

Polyphenol content and *in vitro* radical scavenging activity of some Indian vegetable extracts

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Manuscript received 12 May 2009, accepted 14 June 2010

Abstract : The investigation was undertaken with an objective of analyzing the antioxidant capacity of some vegetables which are taken by the Indians. The polyphenol content of ethanolic extracts was high in ladies finger, fig, green chilies, capsicum, moderate in cucumber, french bean, spinach, ribbed gourd, and skin of ribbed gourd but low in parwal, bitter gourd, snake gourd, pumpkin and brinjal. It has been found that polyphenol content and yield % of parwal skin are both higher than the original vegetable. Parwal skin is consumed after cooking. But skin of ribbed gourd showed a very low polyphenol yield % which is discarded before cooking the vegetable. Reducing power of the flower extracts indicative of electron donating property for termination of free radical chain reactions followed the order : fig < parwal < french bean < bitter gourd < ladies finger. Vegetable extracts also exhibited free radical scavenging activity against the stable free radical cation ABTS^{•+}

Keywords : Antioxidant, polyphenol, ABTS^{•+} radical, free radical scavengers.

Introduction

Polyphenolic compounds constitute one of the largest and most ubiquitous groups of phytochemicals. Ranging from simple phenolic molecules, such as phenolic acids, to highly polymerized compounds with molecular weights of greater than 30000 Da (condensed tannins), the occurrence of this group of substances in plant foods is extremely variable¹. Polyphenols are the most abundant natural antioxidant in the diet which may be 10 times higher than vitamin C and 100 times higher than vitamin E or carotenoids². Natural antioxidants present in foods and other biological materials have attracted considerable interest because of their presumed safety and potential nutritional and therapeutic effects. A considerable body of literature supports a role for oxidative stress in the pathogenesis of age related human diseases and a contribution of dietary polyphenols to their prevention. Health benefits associated with consumption of fruits, vegetables, tea, cocoa and red wines are linked to their polyphenol con-

tent. Recent studies indicated that plant polyphenols, a large group of natural antioxidants, are serious candidates in explanations of the protective effects of vegetables and fruits against cancer and cardiovascular diseases³⁻⁶. Phenolic compounds in red grape wine inhibit *in vitro* oxidation of human low-density lipoprotein (LDL)^{7,8}. Moreover, it has shown that dietary intake of flavonoids is inversely related to coronary heart disease mortality^{9,10}. Epidemiological data as well as *in vitro* studies^{11,12} strongly suggest that food containing phytochemicals with anti-oxidation potential have strong protective effects against major diseases like cancer and cardiovascular diseases. Many common and life threatening human diseases including atherosclerosis, diabetes, cancer and aging have free radical reactions as an underlying mechanism for injury. Generation of oxygen radicals such as superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical and peroxy radicals and reactive non-radical oxygen species such as hydrogen peroxide H₂O₂ and singlet oxygen (¹O₂), as well as

carbon, nitrogen and sulphur radicals comprise the variety of reactive molecules that are associated with cellular and metabolic injury and accelerating aging cancer, cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases and inflammation^{13,14}. Flavonoids, tannins and other phenolic constituents present in food of plant origin are also potential antioxidants¹⁵. The immune system is vulnerable to oxidative stress. During certain diseased states, as well as during aging, there is a need to boost the antioxidant abilities, thereby potentiating the immune mechanism¹⁶.

For many years, polyphenols and their antioxidants were thought to protect cell constituents against oxidative damage through scavenging of free radicals. The increasing interest in the search for natural replacements for synthetic antioxidants has led to the antioxidant evaluation of a number of plant sources. Potential sources of antioxidant compounds have been searched in several types of plant materials such as vegetables, fruits, leaves, oil-seeds, cereal crops, barks and roots, spices and herbs, and crude plant drugs¹⁷. Flavonoids and other plant phenolics, such as phenolic acids, stilbenes, tannins,

lignans, and lignin, are especially common in leaves, flowering tissues, and woody parts such as stems and barks¹⁸. Some Asian vegetables were also studied¹⁹.

India is bestowed with diverse climatic conditions which enable the growth of wide variety of vegetables known for their nutritional values. Extensive study has not been conducted on the antioxidant activity of the extract of vegetables grown in India. The purpose of this study was to screen a large number of vegetables consumed in the Indian diet with respect to their total phenolic content and antioxidant activity. In the present study the antioxidant activity of 13 vegetables and the skin of two vegetables which are regularly consumed by the people were evaluated by widely accepted methods.

Results and discussion

The results of polyphenol analysis of 13 commonly consumed vegetables in India are given in Table 1. The data presented in Table 1 indicates the percentage yield of the polyphenolic extract obtained from the vegetable powder with ethanol : water (80 : 20 v/v). It was com-

Table 1. Yield and polyphenol content of vegetable extracts

Name of vegetables	Family	Edible part	Yield (%)	Polyphenol content (mg/100 g)
Lady's finger (<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i>)	Malvaceae	Skin, flesh, seeds	31.4 ± 1.2	1432.8
Fig (<i>Ficus carica</i>)	Moraceae	Skin, flesh, seeds	20.9 ± 0.9	984.7
Green chili (<i>Capsicum annum</i>)	Solanaceae	Skin and seeds	38.2 ± 1.4	633.4
Capsicum (<i>C. frutescens grossum</i>)	Solanaceae	Skin, flesh, seeds	50.8 ± 2.3	619.5
Cucumber (<i>Cucumis sativus</i>)	Cucurbitaceae	Flesh and seeds	48.4 ± 1.7	445.6
French bean (<i>Vigna sinensis</i>)	Fabaceae	Skin and seeds	29.8 ± 0.7	427.2
Spinach (<i>Spinacia oleraceae</i>)	Brassicaceae	Leaves, stem	10.4 ± 0.4	355.4
Ribbed gourd (<i>Luffa acutangula</i>)	Cucurbitaceae	Flesh and seeds	52.2 ± 1.0	319.2
Peel of ribbed gourd (<i>Luffa acutangula</i>)	Cucurbitaceae	Flesh and seeds	17.2 ± 1.2	314.2
Bitter gourd (<i>Momordica charantia</i>)	Cucurbitaceae	Skin, flesh, seeds	2.4 ± 0.3	181.7
Snake gourd (<i>Tricosanthes anguina</i>)	Cucurbitaceae	Skin, flesh, seeds	41.4 ± 2.1	151.2

Table 1 (contd.)

Parwal (<i>Tricosanthes dioica</i>)	Cucurbitaceae	Flesh and seeds	3.6 ± 0.3	141.4
Peel of parwal (<i>Tricosanthes dioica</i>)	Cucurbitaceae	Flesh and seeds	15.0 ± 0.8	208.1
Pumpkin (<i>Cucurbita moschata</i>)	Solanaceae	Skin, flesh, seeds	10.4 ± 1.1	127.2
Brinjal (<i>Solanum melongen</i>)	Solanaceae	Skin, flesh, seeds	79.0 ± 2.5	103.2

paratively higher in brinjal about 79%. On an average capsicum, cucumber and ribbed gourd contain antioxidant component around ½ of its weight. The polyphenol content of ethanolic extracts was high in ladies finger, fig, green chillies, capsicum, moderate in cucumber, french bean, spinach, ribbed gourd, and skin of ribbed gourd but low in parwal, bitter gourd, snake gourd, pumpkin and brinjal.

The skin of two vegetables ribbed gourd and parwal are also analyzed. It has been found that polyphenol content and yield % of parwal skin are both higher than the original vegetable. Parwal skin is consumed after cooking. But skin of ribbed gourd showed a very low polyphenol yield % which is discarded before cooking the vegetable.

Antioxidant effect exponentially increases as a function of the development of the reducing power, indicating that the antioxidant properties are concomitant with the development of reducing power²⁰. Okuda *et al.*²¹ have reported that tannins inhibit formation of lipid peroxides and prevent liver injury. Reductones react directly with peroxides and also prevent the formation of peroxides by reacting with certain precursors. As seen in Fig. 1 reducing power of ethanol extracts of vegetables increased with increasing concentration from 200 to 400 µg. Reducing power of the vegetables followed the order : fig < parwal < french bean < bitter gourd < ladies finger. The activity of gallic acid was pronouncedly higher than the test samples. Fig. 2 give the reducing power of ethanol extracts of vegetables. In the present study, though the vegetable extracts exhibited a low reducing power they did have an activity that reveals that the vegetables are electron donors and can react with free radicals and convert them to stable products, thus terminating the free radical

Fig. 1. Reducing power of the vegetable extracts.

Fig. 2. Relationship between total polyphenol content and ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging activity.

chain reactions.

Vegetable extracts exhibited free radical scavenging activity against the stable free radical cation ABTS^{•+}. It was reported that the discoloration of the ABTS^{•+} radical cation also reflects the capacity of an antioxidant species to donate electrons or hydrogen atoms to inactivate this radical species^{22,23}. The ABTS^{•+} radical cation is generated from the reaction of ABTS with potassium persulfate overnight in water, followed by dilution with ethanol²². French bean and parwal exhibited nearly similar ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity and is very near to L-ascorbic acid. The other vegetable extracts also showed ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity but the duration of the antioxidant activity of vegetable extracts occurred over a longer duration of time compared to the shorter reaction times of L-ascorbic acid. These differences in kinetic behavior of antioxidant compounds in the ABTS^{•+} free radical model system may be related to the reaction stoichiometry of the number of electrons available to inactivate the free radicals²⁴. Vegetable extracts used in the present study, are hypothesized to have a more complex reaction mechanism involving one or more secondary reactions in the quenching of the ABTS^{•+} radical cations.

Total polyphenol content vs antioxidant activity :

The Folin-Ciocalteu assay for total phenolics correlates positively with the relative antioxidant activity¹⁹. On the contrary, in the present study there was no correlation between the total phenolic content of the vegetable extracts and the antioxidant activity (Pearson correlation $r^2 = -0.238$ and p value = 0.393). Several studies have been made concerning the relationship between the phe-

nolic structures and antioxidant activity^{25,26}, but no relationship has been elucidated because of the many different evaluation systems used to test for antioxidant activity. Heinonen *et al.*²⁷ found that the antioxidant activity of an extract could not be explained just on the basis of their phenolic content but also require their proper characterization. The antioxidant activity of individual phenolic compounds present in the vegetable extracts as well as their synergistic and antagonistic effects together determines the antioxidant activity.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

2,2'-Azino-bis(3-ethyl-benzthiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) cation free radical was purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Company, USA; ascorbic acid, trichloroacetic acid (TCA), ferric chloride (anhydrous) and all the solvents were supplied by E. Merck India Limited. Potassium persulfate, Folin Ciocalteu's phenol reagent, gallic acid, potassium ferricyanide, ethyldiene diaminetetra acetic acid disodium salt (EDTA) were purchased from SRL (Sisco Research Laboratory, India).

Plant samples :

The vegetables were purchased fresh on three separate occasions from local markets of Kolkata, India and was identified by the Department of Botany, University of Calcutta, India.

Extraction for biochemical measurement :

The vegetables were washed thoroughly in tap water, rinsed in distilled water, chopped into small pieces, made into paste by mixer grinder and dried in vacuum oven at 50 ± 2 °C. The dried vegetables were finely powdered. 500 mg of the powder was weighed, homogenized and

Table 2. ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity of the extracts

Vegetables	EC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	Vegetables	EC ₅₀ (mg/ml)
L-Ascorbic acid	0.025	Ladies finger	0.084
French bean	0.038	Green chili	1.04
Spinach	0.095	Cucumber	0.622
Ribbed gourd	0.431	Pumpkin	0.149
Peel of ribbed gourd	0.086	Brinjal	0.547
Parwal	0.042	Capsicum	0.164
Parwal skin	0.082	Bitter gourd	2.376
Fig	0.113	Snake gourd	0.92

extracted with 80 : 20 methanol : water at room temperature and filtered. The residue was re-extracted till the filtrate was colorless. The extracts were pooled and evaporated in a rotary evaporator till free of solvent. The polyphenols obtained were dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water.

Determination of total phenolic content :

The concentration of the phenolic compounds in the extract was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent²⁸. 0.2 and 0.4 mL of the above solution was added to 1 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (diluted by 10 folds), 0.8 mL of 2% Na₂CO₃ was added and the volume made-up to 10 mL using water methanol (4 : 6 v/v) as the diluting fluid. The absorbance was measured at 740 nm after 30 min using Shimadzu (1601A) UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The concentration was calculated using gallic acid as a standard and the results were expressed as gallic acid equivalents per gram extract.

Evaluation of radical scavenging properties of polyphenol extracts :

The reducing power of vegetables was determined according to the method of Oyaizu (1986)²⁹. Different amounts of vegetables (50–250 µg) in 1 mL distilled water was mixed with phosphate buffer (2.5 mL, 0.2 M/L, pH 6.6) and potassium ferricyanide (2.5 mL, 1%). The mixture was incubated at 50 °C for 20 min. 2.5 mL of 10% TCA was added to the mixture. 2.5 mL of this solution was mixed with distilled water (2.5 mL) and FeCl₃ (0.5 mL, 0.1%) and the absorbance was measured at 700 nm. Increased absorbance of the reaction mixture indicated increased reducing power. All analysis was run in triplicates.

The ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity was determined according to Re *et al.*²². Briefly, 5.0 mL 7 mM ABTS was reacted with 88.0 µL 140 mM potassium

persulfate overnight in the dark to yield the ABTS^{•+} radical cation. Prior to use in the assay the ABTS^{•+} was diluted with 50% ethanol for an initial absorbance of 0.7 at 734 nm with temperature control set at 30 °C. Free radical scavenging activity was assayed by mixing 2.0 mL diluted ABTS^{•+} with 20 µL of test antioxidant and monitoring the change in absorbance every minute until a steady state was achieved. The antioxidant capacity of test compounds was expressed as EC₅₀, the concentration necessary for 50% reduction of ABTS^{•+}.

Statistical analysis :

All data are expressed as means ± SEM. Pearson's Correlation was used to test the relationship between polyphenol content and radical scavenging activity.

Acknowledgement

We thank University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India for their financial support.

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